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PLLA honeycombs activated by plasma and high-energy excimer laser for stem cell support

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we constructed and activated honeycomb structures on perfluorinated substrates subjected to KrF laser treatment (wavelength 248 nm). We selected the biopolymer poly L-lactic acid (PLLA) as the honeycomb material, which was dissolved in a mixture of chloroform/methanol. A micropattern of a plasma-treated perfluorethylenepolypropylene (FEP) substrate was prepared by improved phase separation during dip-coating. The PLLA micropattern was subsequently treated with an excimer laser with a laser fluence of 10 mJ.cm⁻² and with a different number of laser pulses. Alternatively, plasma exposure can be used as a secondary treatment. The surface morphologies of the pristine and laser-treated PLLA patterns were studied using atomic force and scanning electron microscopy. The surface chemistry was analyzed using energy-dispersive spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. In addition, the metabolic activity of adipose stem cells was evaluated using the MTS test, and cell numbers in selected samples were determined. The morphology of cells growing in the honeycomb-like pattern was studied in detail using fluorescence microscopy. In all, we used a combination of honeycomb pattern (HCP) laser treatment and plasma treatment to construct an optimal scaffold for adipose stem cell culture.

1. Introduction

The development of micro- and nanopatterns from different materials can be traced back to 1911 to study the effect of topology and fibrous scaffolds on frog embryos [1]. A more recent example is the study of colors found in butterfly wings, which can be artificially reproduced using polystyrene when several gratings are prepared [2] and may be used as photonic materials [3]. The most important procedure is biomimicry, which applies pattern design by mimicking a specific part of an organism [4]. Biomimicking approaches have been used in the medical industry owing to their ability to simulate the desired surface design by applying surface-patterning techniques. Thus, polygon and nanopillar shapes of different dimensions and spacings may be applied to orthopedic implants owing to their antibacterial properties [5], and certain constructed materials may also be used for *in vivo* experiments, where the adhesion of epithelial cells is affected by different properties of

nanoporous surfaces [6]. The selection of material is based on the targeted application, *in vitro* or *in vivo* study, and, more importantly, the type of cell line studied. The primary advantage of applying polymer materials [7–9] is the possibility of easily modifying their surface properties, thus changing both their morphology and surface chemistry [10–12]. The applied procedures may be based on plasma modification, wet techniques based on grafting procedures, or excimer laser exposure, where different patterns, typically linear, dotted, or more complex, may be prepared [13–17].

Different methods were used to create surface patterns of varying sizes and shapes. These methods can be categorized into two main groups: top-down and bottom-up [18]. In addition, they can be integrated with additional techniques or replaced with unconventional patterning methods [19,20]. The top-down approach typically involves removing molecules or atoms from a material using light beams [21–23], and exposure to particles or ions [24]. In contrast, the

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Fig. 1. Scheme of honeycomb pattern formation following laser treatment using excimer laser.

bottom-up approach involves assembling complex structures from molecular or atomic blocks or stacks using assembly processes [25]. Although top-down methods are often more suitable for creating precise patterns on large surfaces, bottom-up approaches tend to produce patterns with fewer defects. Several lithographic techniques, including photolithography, have been used to pattern solid-state substrates, including photolithography [26]. This process involves the chemical modification of UV light and the removal of either the exposed or unexposed regions of the photoresist through chemical etching. Photomasks are frequently modified using digital mirrors [27] or reusable polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) photomasks [28].

Electron-beam lithography (EBL) enables the preparation of high-resolution patterns on a polymer-based resist using focused electron beams, which alter the solubility of the resist and facilitate the selective removal of exposed (positive tone) or non-exposed (negative tone) areas through etching [29,30]. Soft lithography [31,32] encompasses a set of patterning techniques that use soft molds to replicate periodic surface patterns down to approximately 10 nm, apply to flexible surfaces, and are capable of creating patterns over large areas [33]. Key techniques derived from soft lithography include nanoimprint lithography (NIL), which transfers patterns from a master mold to a polymeric resist through mechanical deformation [34–36], and microcontact printing (μ CP), a method that generates surface structures with lateral dimensions ranging from micrometers to nanometers by pressing polymeric surfaces against master stamps [37]. Patterns produced by UV-NIL are highly stable under different conditions and can be applied to fields such as biofilm production and cytocompatibility [38–40].

Not only “classic” polymers but also biopolymers can be patterned into different structures, each exhibiting specific properties that can be used in different biological applications [7,8,9,41,42] and which can also be significantly altered by plasma or laser exposure. Biopolymers such as chitosan, starch, and poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) due to laser irradiation may alter their morphology or porosity [43,44], enabling their use in cell growth procedures. Moreover, specific honeycomb structures may be constructed using improved phase separation techniques such as PLLA, PS, PC, and polyaniline [44–48]. These patterns can be used as templates for lithography techniques or directly applied as substrates for cytocompatibility or antibacterial properties. Biomedical applications of micro/nanopatterned structures are based on the applicability of micro/nanopatterned structures, specifically the patterns that have been formed on the basis of biocompatible or bio-functional polymer materials, with a wide possibility of their studies related to the biomedical field [49–54]. Owing to their interesting

properties and constant advancements made in their design and fabrication, micro- and nano-patterned structures have gained importance both in material and tissue engineering; for example, porous gelatin-based phosphorylated scaffolds have been used for the osteogenic differentiation of human adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells [55]. The paracrine activity of adipose-derived stem cells is modulated by microstructured polymeric fabrics [56]. Microstructured biomaterials have been designed and manufactured based on silicon elastomer-like photoresists and two-photon laser printing [57]. A combination of direct laser writing and nanoimprint lithography was used to control the degradation of polycaprolactone-based micropillar arrays and study stem cell growth on the treated materials [58]. Polypeptide-based microstructured hydrogels support human mesenchymal stem cell growth with high cell viability [59].

We constructed honeycomb scaffolds on a plasma-activated perfluorinated substrate using an improved phase separation technique, which was subsequently used to study the cytocompatibility of stem cells on such surfaces. The advantage of this approach is the synergy based on the subsequent activation of the honeycomb pattern with an excimer laser or argon plasma, with significant changes in both surface morphology and surface chemistry. We have described the cytocompatibility and cell interaction of these honeycomb-altered units with stem cells, which expanded the possibilities of these methods in the field of vascularized tissue substitutes, where ASC stem cells isolated from adipose tissue have the function of pericytes, which support pre-vascularization, *i.e.* the formation of tubular capillary-like structures from endothelial cells in various engineered soft and hard tissues.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and polymer modification

We used perfluoroethylene propylene (FEP) polymer, which was 50 μ m thick and had a density of 2.15 g/cm³. The FEP polymer was supplied by Goodfellow Ltd., UK. Plasma treatment was performed using a diode Ar plasma discharge with a Balzer device. The gas purity was 99.997 %, and the gas pressure was set to 10 Pa. The parameters for plasma discharge were as follows: plasma power of 8 W and electrode distance of 50 mm.

For the construction of honeycomb pattern (HCP), we utilized poly-L-lactic acid obtained from Goodfellow as oriented PLLA foils with a thickness of 50 μ m (density 1.24 g/cm³, $T_g \sim 60$ °C). PLLA solutions were homogenized in an ultrasonic bath (XUBA 1, Grant, UK) for 300 s.

Fig. 2. Surface morphology of pristine and plasma-treated FEP (8 W/240 s). At the bottom left, the surface chemistry from EDS analysis, and at the bottom right, the contact angle of plasma treated and pristine FEP is introduced.

The PLLA microstructures on FEP were created using the dip-coating method. A biopolymer solution based on chloroform and methanol (2 g of PLLA in 100 mL, in a ratio of 85:15) was prepared and mixed with PLLA until a homogeneous solution was obtained.

The polymer samples were irradiated with a KrF laser (Coherent Inc., Leap 100 K, wavelength of 248 nm, pulse duration of 20–40 ns, repetition rate of 10 Hz). We have selected the laser fluence $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, and the number of pulses was selected in the range of 100 to 6000 with the frequency of 10 Hz. A cube of UV-grade fused silica with an active polarization layer was used for polarization.

2.2. Analytical methods

2.2.1. Surface morphology

The surface morphology of materials was examined using an atomic force microscope (Dimension ICON; Bruker Corp.). ScanAsyst® mode in the air was applied with a silicon tip on the Nitride Lever SCANASYST-AIR and a spring constant of $0.4 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$. The acquired data were

processed using the NanoScope Analysis software.

To monitor the material surface morphology, we used the scanning electron microscope LYRA3 GMU (Tescan; Czech Republic) was used. The acceleration voltage was set to 10 kV. Sample metallization was conducted using a sputtering technique (Quorum Q300T equipment) using a Pt conductive layer with a thickness of 10 nm (Pt target, purity 99.9995%).

2.2.2. Wettability and zeta potential

The surface wettability of materials was determined by measuring water contact angles using goniometry. The CA analysis was performed at RT with distilled water at six different positions on three samples using the Surface Energy Evaluation System (Advex Instruments, Czech Republic) with automatic pipetting and a drop volume of $8.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{L}$.

Electrokinetic analysis, more specifically, zeta potential determination of the tested films, was conducted using the SurPASS Instrument (Anton Paar GmbH; Austria) by two methods (streaming current and streaming potential) and calculated using two equations

Fig. 3. Surface morphology of laser exposed PLLA honeycomb pattern on FEP. Samples exposed with a laser fluence of $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the number of laser pulses 100, 500, and 3000 were studied.

Fig. 4. Zeta-potential of pristine honeycombs of PLLA and laser-treated PLLA honeycombs with $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the number of laser pulses 500, 1000, 3000, and 6000. Helmholtz–Smoluchowski (HS) and Fairbrother–Mastin (FM) were used for evaluation.

(Helmholtz–Smoluchowski [HS] and Fairbrother–Mastin [FM]). A comparison of both methods can help evaluate the surface roughness and morphology of the films because the HS equation is strongly affected by sample geometry. The samples were studied inside an adjustable gap

cell with $0.001 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ KCl as an electrolyte at a constant pH of 6.7 at room temperature.

2.2.3. Surface chemistry

The elemental composition of the sample surface was analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using an ESCAProbeP spectrometer (Omicron Nanotechnology). Monochromatic X-rays with an energy of 1486.7 eV Atomic concentrations of elements were determined from the individual peak areas using the CasaXPS software. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to detect the elemental concentration using an F-MaxN analyzer and an SDD detector (Oxford Instruments, UK). The applied acceleration voltage for the EDS was 10 kV. The substrates were covered with a Pt conductive layer of 10 nm thickness by a diode sputtering (Quorum Q300T).

2.3. Cytocompatibility

2.3.1. Cell cultivation on samples

Before cell seeding, tested materials were inserted into 24-well polystyrene plates (TPP, Trasadingen, Switzerland, inner well diameter 1.5 cm) and sterilized by ultra-violet (UV) exposure. The wavelength 260 nm was used, and the sterilization was performed for 15 min. Adipose stem cells (ASCs) were seeded on materials at a seeding density of $25,000 \text{ cells}/\text{cm}^2$ ($50,000 \text{ cells}/\text{sample}$) and cultured for 3 days in the DMEM cultivation medium (Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Sebak GmbH, Aidenbach, Germany) and gentamicin ($40 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, LEK, Ljubljana, Slovenia) at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an air atmosphere with 5% CO_2 . Three independent samples of each type of

Fig. 5. Scanning electron microscopy images of surface morphology of honeycomb-like PLLA pattern on FEP treated with an excimer laser with a laser fluence of $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the number of laser beam pulses 100, 500, 3000, and 6000. The scanning areas were $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, and the detailed images $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ are introduced in the right upper corners.

scaffold were tested.

2.3.2. Evaluation of cell number

On days 1, 2, 3, and 7 after cell seeding, cells on the samples were rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for 15 min. Cell nuclei were visualized by fluorescent DNA staining using DAPI (Sigma Aldrich) for 1 h and imaged using an Olympus IX71 epifluorescence microscope (objective $10 \times$) equipped with a DP 70 digital camera (both from Olympus, Japan), with each

sample in 10 visual fields. The cell number was automatically counted from microphotographs using the Fiji ImageJ software. Statistically significant differences between the data acquired for each surface modification and a parameter (cell viability) were analyzed in Excel using XLSTAT software, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's honest significant difference (HSD) test was used for data modeling of multiple comparisons. All tests were performed with a confidence interval of 0.95. Statistically significant differences were observed between the groups ($P < 0.001$).

Fig. 6. The EDS spectra of a honeycomb-like pattern formed from PLLA on plasma-treated FEP samples subsequently treated with KrF laser with a laser fluence of $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the number of laser pulses 100, 1000, 3000, and 6000. The elemental compositions (in at.%) of prepared patterns are introduced below each spectrum.

2.3.3. Cell morphology

Cell morphology and spreading were evaluated using filamentous actin (F-actin) and visualized by staining cells with phalloidin conjugated with tetramethylrhodamine (TRITC) (Sigma-Aldrich; MO, U.S.A., Cat. no. P1951) to evaluate the assembly of the actin cytoskeleton and the shape and spread of cells on tested materials. Samples were stained for 1 h at room temperature and imaged using an Olympus IX 71 DP 70 digital camera (objective $20\times$) in five representative fields for each of the three independent samples in each experimental group.

2.3.4. Cell metabolic activity

The growth and survival of cells in the tested samples were assessed by measuring their metabolic activity. This is an indirect method for determining the number and proliferation of cells. The activity was measured on days 1, 2, 3, and 7 after seeding the cells using an MTS Cell Proliferation Assay Kit (Colorimetric), cat. no. ab197010 (Abcam; Cambridge, UK) (MTS (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-5-(3-carboxymethoxyphenyl)-2-(4-sulfophenyl)-2H-tetrazolium). This assay measures the reduction of a yellow MTS tetrazolium compound by NAD(P)H-dependent dehydrogenase enzymes in living and metabolically active mammalian cells, resulting in the formation of purple formazan, which is quantified by measuring at the wavelength of 490 nm. Before conducting the assay, the cells were transferred to fresh cell culture plates to eliminate the influence of cell adherence and growth on the bottom of wells under and around the tested samples. The MTS assay was performed according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, the cells were incubated with the MTS reagent for 1 hour. Next, the resulting solution was transferred to 96-well polystyrene test plates (Sigma-Aldrich, $200 \mu\text{L}$ of the solution per well), and the absorbance was measured at 490 nm using the VersaMax ELISA microplate reader (Molecular Devices LLC; Sunnyvale, CA, USA). A sample without cells in each experimental group and time point was used as a control to establish the background for measuring the absorbance. Polystyrene

wells in a 24-well plate were used as reference materials.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Preparation of honeycomb PLLA pattern and substrate properties

In this study, we followed the same procedure as described previously [44], using the FEP polymer as the primary substrate. The pristine polymer, if used for improved phase separation from a mixed solution of chloroform and methanol, does not lead to a sufficiently homogeneous layer.

Plasma preprocessing is an essential step for enhancing the surface properties such that the surface free energy is increased, thus increasing the wettability and decreasing the surface contact angle. From our previously conducted and published experiments, we concluded that the optimal argon plasma power was 8 W, whereas the most homogeneous pattern was generally created for longer exposure times for most of the studied polymers in our group. Therefore, an exposure time of 240 s is the only exposure time that has been used. A schematic of the procedure is shown in Fig. 1. This Figure describes the application of either a KrF excimer laser or plasma treatment on a honeycomb pattern constructed by dip coating, with the aim of surface nanostructuring and changes in surface chemistry.

From Fig. 2, it is evident that exposing the FEP polymer to plasma significantly changes both its surface morphology and chemistry. Plasma exposure induced a wormlike structure on the nanometer scale on the FEP, with a more pronounced effect observed at higher plasma powers and longer exposure times. Specifically, at a plasma power of 8 W and an exposure time of 240 s, the FEP roughness increased to 8.2 nm. These morphological changes were accompanied by changes in the surface chemistry, as indicated by the EDS results in Fig. 2. The pristine FEP surface contained only carbon and fluorine; however, plasma pre-treatment increased the number of oxygen-containing groups on the

Fig. 7. EDS maps (fluorine, carbon, and oxygen) of a honeycomb-like pattern formed from PLLA on plasma-treated FEP samples subsequently treated with KrF laser with a laser fluence of $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the number of laser pulses 1000. In addition, the SEM image of the pattern is introduced.

surface to 14.5%. In addition, a small amount of nitrogen was deposited on the surface. A decrease in fluorine was accompanied by an increase in oxygen- and nitrogen-containing groups, as the fluorine atoms were replaced by oxygen in the upper modified layers. These changes in the surface morphology and chemical composition drastically decreased the surface wettability, as shown at the bottom right of Fig. 2. The hydrophobic FEP surface turned hydrophilic as the contact angle decreased to 34° . These significant changes in the physicochemical properties of the FEP surface provide a strong basis for the construction of honeycomb biopolymer films, as will be further discussed in the paper.

3.1.1. Surface morphology-AFM

Such treated surfaces can be easily used to construct honeycomb patterns by applying an improved phase separation method, which has been successfully applied to the biopolymers polystyrene [44] and cellulose acetate [46]. Based on previously published results, we decided to prepare the honeycomb PLLA pattern using 2 g of PLLA in a volume solution (by volume 85:15–chloroform and methanol). This honeycomb pattern was stable with optimal pattern homogeneity. In this research, we decided to apply the same procedure of the plasma surface modification used for the exposure of the primary substrate and to apply it as a “secondary” surface modification of the already formed surface

Fig. 8. XPS spectra of a honeycomb-like pattern formed from PLLA on plasma-treated FEP samples subsequently treated with KrF laser with laser fluence $10 \text{ mJ} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$, pristine honeycomb pattern (a) and the pattern treated with the number of laser pulses 1000 (b), 3000 (c), and 6000 (d) are introduced. Elemental compositions (in at.%) of treated patterns are also introduced.

honeycomb pattern or to use an excimer laser as a secondary treatment. Because significant surface changes were observed with the application of an excimer laser to polystyrene honeycombs [44], we decided to study this modification procedure for PLLA honeycombs. Based on the previously achieved results, we have selected the laser fluence $10 \text{ mJ} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ as the energy of the excimer beam with pulses varying from 100 to 6000.

Excimer laser treatment of the constructed honeycomb units of the FEP substrate changed the surface morphology, as shown in Fig. 3. A lower number of laser pulses led to only minor changes in the honeycomb unit morphology. With a larger number of laser pulses, we can observe the partial disruption of the honeycomb unit; certain “walls” are disrupted, the pattern shape is still maintained, and the process is complemented with a slight increase in surface roughness (up to 292 nm). With a substantial increase in the number of laser pulses up to 3000, we observed a disruption of the pattern, although the primary honeycomb shape was preserved, which is an important parameter for the subsequent study of cytocompatibility.

3.2. Zeta-potential

The synergistic effect of surface chemistry and morphology changes dramatically modified the zeta potential, as shown in Fig. 4. The formation of honeycombs dramatically increased the zeta potential of the surface compared to that of the pristine FEP (green line), and the surface became more hydrophilic. The zeta potential values for both HS and FM

were not different, which implies no changes in the charge of the surface on altered substrates. The increase in the number of laser pulses (increase in laser dose) reduced the zeta potential values, and a steady decrease was observed up to the number of laser pulses (6000), with the value of the zeta potential even lower (higher in absolute value) than that of the pristine PLLA honeycomb pattern on FEP.

3.3. SEM and EDS analyses

In addition, surface morphology changes were studied with SEM, and the results are shown in Fig. 5. If we increase the number of laser pulses, no significant changes in the surface morphology of the honeycomb pattern were observed for a lower number of pulses (first line in Fig. 5).

The unit structure was preserved until the number of pulses reached 500. However, even after 500 pulses, we could observe certain changes in the pattern morphology. These changes were strongly induced for more than 3000 pulses (bottom line of Fig. 5). The major pattern diminishes owing to two major factors. The first factor was laser-induced ablation [60], which was previously determined for laser-exposed biopolymers PLLA and PHB. However, as it is evident, in this case, the melting of PLLA material is also induced, probably due to an increase in the surface temperature above $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is the glass transition temperature of the studied biopolymer. The application of 6000 laser pulses led to an even more pronounced distortion of the honeycomb units, which formed an almost continuous layer on the plasma-treated FEP substrate.

Fig. 9. Fluorescence images of adipose stem cell 3 days post-seeding on PLLA honeycomb matrices treated by excimer laser with a fluence of $10 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the number of laser pulses 500, 1000, and 3000. Nuclei stained with DAPI are in blue, and F-actin labeled with phalloidin-Atto 488 is in green. Scale is introduced within each image.

In addition, the laser-induced significant changes in the surface chemistry, as is visible in the EDS spectra (Fig. 6) and the EDS mapping of the honeycomb structure after 1000 pulses (Fig. 7). From Fig. 7, we can conclude that for a lower laser dose (up to 1000 laser pulses), there is a mild increase in oxygen concentration, which is induced by the distortion of the biopolymer bond by the excimer energy; the disconnected bonds with radicals tend to interact with the oxygen atmosphere, thus creating oxygen-containing groups. With the application of a higher number of laser pulses, this effect is suppressed, and the major effect is the reorientation of the polymeric chains due to exceeding the glass transition temperature or the ablation of the biopolymer layer when the most modified layer is released from the surface due to ablation effect.

However, as shown in the morphology images in Fig. 6 and, more importantly, the EDS mapping (Fig. 7), the continuous PLLA layer became discontinuous, and the plasma-treated FEP surface, which

served as the basic substrate, was revealed. This effect is the key factor for the decrease in the oxygen concentration for a higher number of applied laser pulses, which is accompanied by an increase in the fluorine atomic concentration from the FEP substrate. We determined only 4.56% of oxygen for the honeycomb pattern which was treated with 6000 pulses.

3.4. XPS analysis

In addition, the surface chemistry was determined using X-ray photoelectron chemistry (Fig. 8), which can reveal information from the top surface up to only 10 atomic layers, which is approximately 1 nm. The surface chemistry of a pristine PLLA honeycomb pattern without laser exposure was determined. Even on such a surface, we determined the nonzero fluorine concentration, which revealed that the honeycomb

Fig. 10. Cell metabolic activity–MTS test, for pristine PLLA honeycomb-like pattern on FEP (0), and honeycombs treated with excimer laser with a fluence of 10 mJ.cm⁻² and the number of pulses ranging from 500 to 6000, or PLLA honeycomb treated with argon plasma (8 W and 240 s). In addition, results for pristine PLLA foil (pristine) and tissue polystyrene (PS) are included. The results are shown for days 1, 2, 3, and 7 after seeding. Mean ± SD of 4 wells. One-way ANOVA, all pairwise multiple comparison procedures (Student-Newman-Keuls Method), *p* ≤ 0.05. Samples were statistically compared on the same day after seeding. Statistically significant differences are shown above the bars. The symbol • indicates a significant difference from sample 6000, # from the control pristine sample, and * from the control polystyrene (PS) sample.

pattern was not monotonously continuous in the FEP substrate. However, the amount of fluorine is very small; therefore, the amount of exposed substrate is also small. With an increasing number of laser pulses, it is evident that the fluorine concentration increased; however, there is no trend, and there is no direct correlation between the number of laser pulses and fluorine concentration. This surprising fact is probably based on two facts. First, the information is taken from the very top surface; therefore, even if the honeycomb structure is disrupted, the

fluorine concentration does not increase significantly because a layer of PLLA with a small thickness remains on the exposed FEP substrate even for a higher number of laser pulses (e.g., 6000). Second, the FEP substrate, which was treated with plasma (8 W for 240 s), also increased the atomic oxygen concentration even before the honeycomb was constructed.

3.5. Cytocompatibility

The main aim of this study was to investigate the cytocompatibility of laser-exposed samples. First, we presented detailed images of stem cells grown on the laser-exposed honeycomb pattern (Fig. 9). The morphology of stem cells revealed that the shape was optimal for all laser-treated samples. Only representative samples were selected to show the detailed morphology of cells and their attachment to laser-treated samples. For the primary evaluation of the cytocompatibility of laser-treated honeycombs, we used the MTS test.

Fig. 10

This assay is a colorimetric assay for assessing cell metabolic activity; this assay is often described as a “one-step” MTT assay, offering the convenience of adding the reagent straight to the cell culture without intermittent steps required in the MTT assay. The cell viability on subsequently treated honeycomb substrates is comparable to that on the pristine honeycomb pattern and to that on control PS. There was a significant reduction in the initial cell growth phase (day 1) for the sample exposed to 6000 laser pulses. After 3 days of cultivation, however, we observed significantly increased metabolic activity on all laser-treated samples compared to the PS control, and in the case of the sample exposed to 6000 laser pulses, also a significant increase compared to the pristine sample. In each group of samples monitored, the metabolic activity increased over time, but by day 7, the cells had already entered a phase of slower growth, where the increase in their metabolic activity, and therefore the effect of the substrates, was less apparent.

The cytocompatibility of laser-treated honeycomb samples is shown in Fig. 11, along with the results of the honeycomb pattern that was plasma-treated under conditions introduced in the previous paragraph. The laser and plasma treatments did not significantly affect cell adhesion

Fig. 11. Cell adhesion and proliferation determination–number of cells for pristine PLLA honeycomb-like pattern on FEP (0), and honeycombs treated with excimer laser with fluence of 10 mJ.cm⁻² and number of pulses 500–6000, or PLLA honeycomb treated with argon plasma (8 W and 240 s), also results for pristine PLLA foil (pristine) and tissue polystyrene (PS) are introduced. The results are shown for days 1, 2, 3, and 7 after seeding. ANOVA + Tukey (HSD) analysis of the differences between the categories with a confidence interval of 95%.

or the first stage of cell proliferation. When we examined cell numbers until the second day after seeding, no significant changes were observed. However, the proliferation of the pristine PLLA sample was lower than that of treated samples 3 days after seeding. Seven days after seeding, significant differences were observed in cytocompatibility among the selected samples. Interesting results were obtained for the honeycomb pattern, which was subsequently studied with plasma; the cytocompatibility was higher than that of PLLA honeycombs, but more importantly to tissue polystyrene. The cell number determined on PLLA honeycombs treated with an excimer laser with 1000 pulses was also better than that on tissue culture polystyrene.

4. Conclusions

In this study, PLLA honeycomb-type microstructures were prepared on the surfaces of plasma-treated FEP and subsequently treated with an excimer laser of additive plasma exposure. PLLA pattern formation was induced by improving phase separation using the dip-coating technique. The additional excimer exposure with laser fluence of 10 mJ.cm^{-2} did not affect the honeycomb shape significantly till the number of pulses reached 1000, with a higher number of applied laser pulses due to ablation, and more importantly, surface local melting above PLLA glass transition temperature causing the structure to partially collapse. Even at low integral laser doses, the surface chemistry and wettability of honeycomb patterns were significantly affected. The cell viability on subsequently treated honeycomb substrates is comparable to that on the pristine honeycomb pattern and to that on control PS. There was a significant reduction in the initial cell growth phase (day 1) for the sample exposed to 6000 laser pulses. After 3 days of cultivation, however, we observed significantly increased metabolic activity on all laser-treated samples compared to the PS control, and in the case of the sample exposed to 6000 laser pulses, also a significant increase compared to the pristine sample.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Slepíčka: Writing – original draft, Supervision. **N. Slepíčková Kasálková:** Writing – review & editing. **J. Musílková:** Investigation. **L. Bačáková:** Investigation. **B. Frýdlová:** Investigation. **P. Sajdl:** Investigation. **Z. Kolská:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **E. Rebollar:** Methodology, Investigation. **V. Švorčík:** Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data presented in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14020478>.

References

- [1] R. McMurray, M.J. Dalby, and N. Gadegaard, *Nanopatterned Surfaces for Biomedical Applications*, in book: *Biomedical Engineering, Trends in Materials Science*, edited by Anthony N. Laskovski, Vol. 22 IntechOpen (2011), <https://doi.org/10.5772/13453>.
- [2] S. Chen, B. Haehle, X. Van der Laan, A.J.C. Kuehne, I. Botiz, P.N. Stavrinou, N. Stingelin, Understanding hierarchical spheres-in-grating assembly for bio-inspired colouration, *Mater. Horiz.* 8 (2021) 2230.
- [3] E.S.A. Goerlitzer, R.N. Klupp, N. Vogel Taylor, Bioinspired photonic pigments from colloidal self-assembly, *Adv. Mater.* 30 (2018) 1706654.
- [4] M.S. Aziz, A.Y. El, sherif, Biomimicry as an approach for bio-inspired structure with the aid of computation, *Alex. Eng. J.* 55 (2016) 707.
- [5] A. Jaggesar, H. Shahali, A. Mathew, P.K.D.V. Yarlagadda, Bio-mimicking nano and micro-structured surface fabrication for antibacterial properties in medical implants, *J. Nanobiotechnol.* 15 (2017) 64.
- [6] A. Fattah-Alhosseini, R. Chaharmahali, S. Alizad, M. Kaseem, B. Dikici, A review of smart polymeric materials: recent developments and prospects for medicine applications, *Hybrid Adv.* 5 (2024) 100178.
- [7] P. Slepíčka, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, J. Siegel, Z. Kolská, L. Bacáková, V. Švorčík, Nano-structured and functionalized surfaces for cytocompatibility improvement and bactericidal action, *Biotechnol. Adv.* 33 (2015) 1120–1129.
- [8] P. Slepíčka, J. Siegel, O. Lyutakov, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, Z. Kolská, L. Bacáková, V. Švorčík, Polymer nanostructures for bioapplications induced by laser treatment, *Biotechnol. Adv.* 36 (2018) 839–855.
- [9] D. Fajstavr, K. Fajstavrová, B. Frýdlová, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, V. Švorčík, P. Slepíčka, Biopolymer honeycomb microstructures: a review, *Materials (Basel)* 16 (2023) 772–797.
- [10] P. Chytrosz-Wrobel, M. Golda-Cepa, E. Stodolak-Zych, J. Rysz, A. Kotarba, Effect of oxygen plasma-treatment on surface functional groups, wettability, and nanotopography features of medically relevant polymers with various crystallinities, *Appl. Surf. Sci. Adv.* 18 (2023) 100497.
- [11] J. Lišková, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, P. Slepíčka, V. Švorčík, L. Bačáková, Heat-treated carbon coatings on poly (L-lactide) foils for tissue engineering, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 100 (2019) 117–128.
- [12] P. Žáková, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, P. Slepíčka, Z. Kolská, J. Karpíšková, V. Švorčík I.Stibor, Cytocompatibility of polyethylene grafted with triethylenetetramine functionalized carbon nanoparticles, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 422 (2017) 809–816.
- [13] S. Lai, Y. Liu, L. Gong, Y. Zhao, Ch. Zhang, B. Han, Laser-induced surface structures at polymer surfaces irradiated by ns-UV-laser in water confinement and in air, *Optics. Laser Technol.* 168 (2024) 109871.
- [14] M. Ehrhardt, S. Lai, P. Lorenz, K. Zimmer, Guiding of LIPSS formation by excimer laser irradiation of pre-patterned polymer films for tailored hierarchical structures, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 506 (2020) 144785.
- [15] P. Slepíčka, A. Chaloupka, P. Sajdl, J. Heitz, V. Hnatowicz, V. Švorčík, Angle dependent laser nanopatterning of poly(ethylene terephthalate) surfaces, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 257 (2011) 6021–6025.
- [16] E. Rebollar, M. Castillejo, T.A. Ezquerro, Laser induced periodic surface structures on polymer films: from fundamentals to applications, *Eur. Polym. J.* 73 (2015) 162–174.
- [17] E. Rebollar, S. Pérez, M. Hernández, C. Domingo, M. Martín, T.A. Ezquerro, M. Castillejo, M. Physicochemical modifications accompanying UV laser induced surface structures on poly(ethylene terephthalate) and their effect on adhesion of mesenchymal cells, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 16 (2014) 17551.
- [18] S. Mohapatra, R.S. Moirangthem, Fabrication of flexible and economical plasmonic biosensor using gold nanograting imprinted on hot-melt adhesive film for label-free sensing of immunoglobulin proteins, *Sens. Actuat. B Chem.* 301 (2019) 127070.
- [19] Q. Liu, X. Zhou, H. Wu, L. Wu, B. Zheng, A polydopamine patterned perfluoropolymer-based substrate for protein microarray applications, *Sens. Actuat. B Chem.* 287 (2019) 306.
- [20] P. Beyazkılıç, A. Saateh, M. Bayindir, C. Elbuken, Evaporation-induced biomolecule detection on versatile superhydrophilic patterned surfaces: glucose and DNA assay, *ACS Omega* 3 (2018) 13503.
- [21] W. Hawkes, D. Huang, P. Reynolds, L. Hammond, M. Ward, N. Gadegaard, J. F. Marshall, T. Iskratsch, M. Palma, Probing the nanoscale organisation and multivalency of cell surface receptors: DNA origami nanoarrays for cellular studies with single-molecule control, *Faraday Discuss.* 219 (2019) 203.
- [22] X. Zhang, B. Wang, L. Huang, W. Huang, Z. Wang, W. Zhu, Y. Chen, Y. Mao, A. Facchetti, T.J. Marks, Breath figure-derived porous semiconducting films for organic electronics, *Sci. Adv.* 6 (2020) eaaz1042.
- [23] S. Park, M. Notaros, A. Mohanty, D. Kim, J. Notaros, S. Mouradian, Technologies for modulation of visible light and their applications, *Prog. Quant. Electron.* 97 (2024) 100534.
- [24] A. Kolander, H. Schiff, G. Gruetzner, Mr-PosEBR: a novel positive tone resist for high resolution electron beam lithography and 3D surface patterning, *Proc. SPIE* 9779 (2016) 977925.
- [25] K. Nickmans, A.P.H.J. Schenning, Directed self-assembly of liquid-crystalline molecular building blocks for sub-5 Nm nanopatterning, *Adv. Mater.* 30 (2018) 1703713.
- [26] M. Fromel, R.L. Crisci III, Ch.S. Sankhe, D. Reifsnnyder Hickey, T.B. Tighe, E. W. Gomez, Ch.W. Pester, User-friendly chemical patterning with digital light projection polymer brush photolithography, *Eur. Polym. J.* 158 (2021) 110652.
- [27] K. Holz, E. Schaudy, J. Lietard, M.M. Somoza, Multi-level patterning nucleic acid photolithography, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019) 3805.

- [28] T.Y. Jeon, H.C. Jeon, S.Y. Lee, T.S. Shim, J.-D. Kwon, S.-G. Park, S.-M. Yang, 3D hierarchical architectures prepared by single exposure through a highly durable colloidal phase mask, *Adv. Mater.* 26 (2014) 1422.
- [29] R. Kirchner, V. Guzenko, H. Schift, Single-digit 6-Nm multilevel patterns by electron beam grayscale lithography, *Adv. Opt. Technol.* 8 (2019) 175.
- [30] X. Wu, F. Teng, M. Libera, Functional changes during electron-beam lithography of biotinylated poly(ethylene glycol) thin films, *ACS Macro Lett* 8 (2019) 1252.
- [31] A. Pandey, S. Tzadka, D. Yehuda, M. Schwartzman, Soft thermal nanoimprint with 10 Nm feature size, *Soft Matter* 15 (2019) 2897.
- [32] A.K. Ferchichi, M. Panabi'ere, O. Desplats, C. Gourgon, Fabrication of superhydrophobic surfaces on flexible fluorinated foils by using dual-scale patterning, *Mater. Res. Express* 1 (2014) 025704.
- [33] M. Leitgeb, D. Nees, S. Ruttloff, U. Palfinger, J. Gotz, R. Liska, M.R. Beleggras, B. Stadlober, Multi-length scale patterning of functional layers by roll-to-roll ultraviolet-light assisted nanoimprint lithography, *ACS Nano* 10 (2016) 4926.
- [34] J. Ko, et al., Nanotransfer printing on textile substrate with water-soluble polymer nanotemplate, *ACS Nano* 14 (2020) 2191.
- [35] R. Cai, V.-A. Antohe, B. Nysten, L. Piraux, A.M. Jonas, Thermally induced flexo-type effects in nanopatterned multiferroic layers, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 30 (2020) 1910371.
- [36] C. Farcau, D. Marconi, A. Colnița, I. Brezeștean, L. Barbu-Tudoran, Gold nanopost-shell arrays fabricated by nanoimprint lithography as a flexible plasmonic sensing platform, *Nanomaterials* 9 (2019) 1519.
- [37] N. Pallab, S. Reinicke, J. Gurke, R. Rihm, S. Kogikoski, M. Hartlieb, M. Reifarth, Polymer brush-assisted microcontact printing: using a tailor-made polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamp for precise patterning of rough surfaces, *Polym. Chem.* 15 (2024) 853–867.
- [38] H.-H. Park, K. Sun, M. Seong, M. Kang, S. Park, S. Hong, H. Jung, J. Jang, J. Kim, H. E. Jeong, Lipid-hydrogel-nanostructure hybrids as robust biofilm-resistant polymeric materials, *ACS Macro Lett.* 8 (2018) 64.
- [39] I.M. Handrea-Dragan, I. Botiz, A.S. Tatar, S. Boca, Patterning at the micro/nano-scale: polymeric scaffolds for medical diagnostic and cell-surface interaction applications, *Colloids Surf. B* 218 (2022) 112730.
- [40] H.Y. Gong, J. Park, W. Kim, J. Kim, J.Y. Lee, W.-G. Koh, A novel conductive and micropatterned PEG-based hydrogel enabling the topographical and electrical stimulation of myoblasts, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (2019) 47695.
- [41] R. Makita, T. Akasaka, S. Tamagawa, Y. Yoshida, S. Miyata, H. Miyaji, T. Sugaya, Preparation of micro/nanopatterned gelatins crosslinked with genipin for biocompatible dental implants, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 9 (2018) 1735.
- [42] D. Sanchez, de Alcazar, et al., Engineered protein-based functional nanopatterned materials for bio-optical devices, *Nanoscale Adv.* 1 (2019) 3980.
- [43] M. Castillejo, E. Rebolgar, M. Oujja, M. Sanz, A. Selimis, M. Sygletou, S. Psycharakis, A. Ranella, C. Fotakis, Fabrication of porous biopolymer substrates for cell growth by UV laser: the role of pulse duration, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 258 (2012) 8919.
- [44] P. Slepicka, K. Neznalová, D. Fajstavr, V. Švorčík, Nanostructuring of honeycomb-like polystyrene with excimer laser, *Prog. Organic Coat.* 145 (2020) 105670.
- [45] G.H. Nguyen Hoang, N.M. Chau, T. Van Le, V.T. Bui, T.T. Ha, La, Large-area customizable honeycomb patterned polycarbonate derived from roofing sheet waste for a slippery liquid-infused porous surface, *Polymer* 285 (2023) 126321.
- [46] K. Neznalová, P. Sajdl, V. Švorčík, P. Slepicka, Cellulose acetate honeycomb-like pattern created by improved phase separation, *Express Polym. Lett.* 14 (2020) 1078–1088.
- [47] T.H. Le, N.M. Chau, T.V. Le, N.H. Hieu, V.T. Bui, Water transferable, customizable highly ordered honeycomb film from polystyrene foam waste for complex surface patterning in confined space, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 141 (2024) e55241.
- [48] S. Falak, B.K. Shin, D.S. Huh, Antibacterial activity of polyaniline coated in the patterned film depending on the surface morphology and acidic dopant, *Nanomaterials* 12 (2022) 1085.
- [49] Z. Wang, J. Xia, S. Luo, P. Zhang, Z. Xiao, T. Liu, J. Guan, Versatile surface micropatterning and functionalization enabled by microcontact printing of poly(4-aminostyrene), *Langmuir* 30 (2014) 13483.
- [50] S. Park, J.A. Jackman, X. Xu, P.S. Weiss, N.-J. Cho, Micropatterned viral membrane clusters for antiviral drug evaluation, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (2019) 13984.
- [51] M.C. Echave, C. Pimenta-Lopes, J.L. Pedraz, M. Mehrali, A. Dolatshahi-Pirouz, F. Ventura, G. Orive, Enzymatic crosslinked gelatin 3D scaffolds for bone tissue engineering, *Int. J. Pharm.* 562 (2019) 151.
- [52] A.A. Kohestani, Z. Xu, F.E. Baştan, A.R. Boccaccini, F. Pishbin, Electrically conductive coatings in tissue engineering, *Acta Biomater.* 186 (2024) 30–62.
- [53] R. Pugliese, S. Graziosi, Biomimetic scaffolds using triply periodic minimal surface-based porous structures for biomedical applications, *SLAS Technol.* 28 (2023) 165–182.
- [54] Pieter Cools, Nathalie De Geyter, Rino Morent, Non-thermal plasma assisted lithography for biomedical applications: an overview, *Int. J. Nanotechnol.* 13 (2016) 695.
- [55] B. Safari, A. Aghanejad, Porous gelatin-based phosphorylated scaffold: microstructure, cell response and osteogenic differentiation of human adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells, *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.* 99 (2024) 106008.
- [56] F. Grilli, E. Albanesi, B. Pelacho, F. Prosper, P. Decuzzi, D. Di Mascolo, Microstructured polymeric fabrics modulating the paracrine activity of adipose-derived stem cells, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24 (2023) 10123.
- [57] N. Munding, M. Fladung, Y. Chen, M. Hippler, A.D. Ho, M. Wegener, M. Bastmeyer, M. Tanaka, Bio-metamaterials for mechano-regulation of mesenchymal stem cells, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 34 (2024) 2301133.
- [58] N. Geoghegan, M. O'Loughlin, C. Delaney, K.D. Rochfort, M. Kennedy, S. Kolagatla, L. Podhorska, B.J. Rodriguez, L. Florea, S.M. Kelleher, Controlled degradation of polycaprolactone based micropillar arrays, *Biomater. Sci.* 11 (2023) 3077.
- [59] S.S. Patkar, C.G. Garcia, L.L. Palmese, K.L. Kiick, Sequence-encoded differences in phase separation enable formation of resilin-like polypeptide-based microstructured hydrogels, *Biomacromolecules* 24 (2023) 3729–3741.
- [60] I. Michaljanicová, P. Slepicka, J. Heitz, R.A. Barb, P. Sajdl, V. Švorčík, Comparison of KrF and ArF excimer laser treatment of biopolymer surface, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 339 (2015) 144–150.